

Islamic Mutual Financial Assistance (*Takaful*): Benefits and Challenges of the Association of Model Islamic Schools (AMIS), Taraba State Chapter

Abdullahi, Yusuf Usman Ph.D.¹

Email: abdullahiyusuf50@gmail.com; muhdusman064@yahoo.com

Tel: +238036203504

Umar, Lubabatu²

¹Department of Islamic Studies, Taraba State University, Jalingo.

²Department of Arts Education, Taraba State University, Jalingo

Abstract

This paper discusses Islamic mutual financial assistance (*Takaful*): benefits and challenges of the Association of Model Islamic Schools (AMIS), Taraba State Chapter, and how it helps in wealth creation. Most Islamic scholars opined that conventional insurance is unacceptable in Islam because it does not conform to *shari'ah*, for it has some element of uncertainty *al-gharar*. Conventional insurance is based on the concept and practice of charging interest. It is common knowledge among the Muslim society that *riba* interest is something abhorrent in Islam and there is no doubt that the loan facilities available in conventional banks are not meeting the required motives of Muslims as the facilities are surrounded with interest. This paper therefore brings to light the significance of mutual financial assistance among AMIS members which is devoid of interest and it benefits of wealth creation. This is in line with the Islamic principles of (*ta awanu alal-birri*), as enshrined in the Qur'an and Sunnah. The paper concludes that mutual assistance among AMIS Members helps in wealth creation and sustainable economic development. The paper recommends that Muslim organizations, groups and individuals should embrace this spirit of mutual financial assistance by pooling their resources to create wealth.

Keywords: *Takaful*, Practice, Wealth Creation, Sustainable Development.

Introduction

Takaful (التكافل) originates from Arabic word, "*Kafalah*" which means "guaranteeing each other" or joint guarantee". Technically, the concept of *Takaful* in the area of insurance means mutual assurance or guarantee amongst the members of a group. It is basically the pooling of resources to assist brethren who are in need. It is also seen as a mutual agreement between two parties for a mutual cooperation in protecting one's life or property from any unprotected or unavoidable risk, danger or tragedy (Musa A, 2014:24). In other word *takaful* is a co-operative system of re-imburement or repayment in case of loss, paid to people and companies. It is concerned with mutual assistance among members, who are faced with hazard; from a fund manage by a *takaful* operator (Musa, 2014). It is commonly defined as an Islamic insurance concept which is grounded in Islamic *mu'amalat* (Islamic activities), observing the rules and regulations of Islamic law. Eventually, a number of models of *takaful* have been formulated overtime, namely *mudarabah*, modified *mudarabah*, *wakalah* and *wakalah-waqf*. There is no doubt that the system of *takaful* have recorded a lot of successes among it's operators around the globe. The recent re-emergences of *takaful* companies add up further to the rapid growth in *takaful* operators and funds.

Takaful in the Glorious Qur'an and Sunnah

Different portions in the Glorious Qur'an speak about *takaful* in the context of co-operation and solidarity for the good of society. One generally quoted reference is from *Surah Ma'idah*, where Allah the exalted says:

وَتَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْبِرِّ وَالتَّقْوَىٰ وَلَا تَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْإِثْمِ وَالْعُدْوَانِ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ إِنَّ اللَّهَ شَدِيدُ الْعِقَابِ (2)

And help one another in righteousness and piety and do not help one another in evil deeds and enmity (Q:5: 2)

The above verse mentions the tradition of mutual assistance in Islam which enhances the spirit of co-operation in the Muslim society. Accordingly, the Madinan charter gave emphasized to the spirit of co-operation between the *Ansar* of Madina and the *Muhajirun* of Makkah, so much so that the mutual dealings among them looks like blood relative i.e. in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness, justice and mutual responsibility. In this regard, Allah the exalted says:

وَالَّذِينَ تَبَوَّءُوا الدَّارَ وَالْإِيمَانَ مِنْ قَبْلِهِمْ يُحِبُّونَ مَنْ هَاجَرَ إِلَيْهِمْ وَلَا يَجِدُونَ فِي صُدُورِهِمْ حَاجَةً مِمَّا أُوتُوا وَيُؤْتُونَ عَلَى
أَنْفُسِهِمْ وَلَوْ كَانَ بِهِمْ خَصَاصَةٌ وَمَنْ يُوقِ شَحْنًا نَفْسِهِ فَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْمُفْلِحُونَ (9)

But those who before them had homes (in Madina) and had adopted the faith, show their affection to such as come to them for refuge, and entertain no desire in their hearts for things given to the (latter), but give them preference over themselves, even though poverty was their (own lot) and those saved from the covetousness of their own souls; they are the ones that achieve prosperity. (Q.59: 9)

Islam aims at establishing social order under universal brotherhood. The fundamental concept is that of mutual co-operation and help. The Prophet (SAW) is reported to have said in the following tradition:

حَدَّثَنَا مُحَمَّدُ بْنُ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ بْنِ نُمَيْرٍ، حَدَّثَنَا أَبِي، حَدَّثَنَا زَكَرِيَاءُ، عَنِ الشَّعْبِيِّ، عَنِ الثُّعْمَانِ بْنِ بَشِيرٍ، قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ
" مَثَلُ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ فِي تَوَادُّهِمْ وَتَرَاحُمِهِمْ وَتَعَاطُفِهِمْ مَثَلُ الْجَسَدِ إِذَا اشْتَكَى مِنْهُ عُضْوٌ تَدَاعَى لَهُ سَائِرُ الْجَسَدِ بِالسَّهْرِ وَالْحُمَى "

Nu'man b. Bashir reported Allah's Messenger (ﷺ) as saying: The similitude of believers in regard to mutual love, affection, fellow-feeling is that of one body; when any limb of it aches, the whole-body aches, because of sleeplessness and fever. (Sahih Muslim 2586, Book 45, Hadith 84)

Other relevant references to *Takaful* in the glorious Qur'an are as follows:

الَّذِي أَطْعَمَهُمْ مِنْ جُوعٍ وَأَمَّنَّهُمْ مِنْ خَوْفٍ (4)

(Allah) who prepares nourishment to prevent the fear of hunger and saves / puts at peace those who fear (Q. 106:4)

The verse shows that *takaful* is similar to a protection against any eventual calamity among the contributing members. Muslims are therefore like brothers in their dealings, one part is supporting the other part. As can be seen in the following Qur'anic statement:

إِنَّمَا الْمُؤْمِنُونَ إِخْوَةٌ فَأَصْلِحُوا بَيْنَ أَخَوَيْكُمْ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ لَعَلَّكُمْ تُرْحَمُونَ (10)

The believers are but a single brotherhood: so make peace and reconciliation between your two (contending) brothers; and fear Allah, that you may receive mercy. (Q.49 10)

A fellow Muslim is always supporting his fellow Muslim. He should neither commit oppression upon him, nor ruin him. And he who meets the needs of a brother, Allah would meet his needs and he who relieves his brother from hardship, Allah will relieve him from the hardships to which he could be put on the Day of Resurrection. This is authentically reported in the following Prophetic tradition:

عَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ مَنْ نَفَسَ عَنْ مُؤْمِنٍ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ الدُّنْيَا نَفَسَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ يَوْمِ
الْقِيَامَةِ وَمَنْ يَسِّرْ عَلَى مُعْسِرٍ يَسَّرَ اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ وَمَنْ سَتَرَ مُسْلِمًا سَتَرَهُ اللَّهُ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ وَاللَّهُ فِي عَوْنِ الْعَبْدِ مَا
كَانَ الْعَبْدُ فِي عَوْنِ أَخِيهِ وَمَنْ سَلَكَ طَرِيقًا يَلْتَمِسُ فِيهِ عِلْمًا سَهَّلَ اللَّهُ لَهُ بِهِ طَرِيقًا إِلَى الْجَنَّةِ وَمَا اجْتَمَعَ قَوْمٌ فِي بَيْتٍ مِنْ بُيُوتِ اللَّهِ
يَتْلُونَ كِتَابَ اللَّهِ وَيَتَدَارَسُونَ بَيْنَهُمْ إِلَّا نَزَلَتْ عَلَيْهِمُ السَّكِينَةُ وَغَشِيَتْهُمُ الرَّحْمَةُ وَحَفَّتْهُمُ الْمَلَائِكَةُ وَذَكَرَهُمُ اللَّهُ فِيمَنْ عِنْدَهُ وَمَنْ بَطَأَ بِهِ
عَمَلُهُ لَمْ يَسْرِعْ بِهِ نَسِيَهُ

صحيح مسلم كتاب الذكر والدعاء والتوبة والاستغفار باب فضل الاجتماع على تلاوة القرآن وعلى الذكر 2699

On the authority of Abu Huraira (May Allah be pleased with him) from the Prophet (SAW) who said, " Whoever relieves a believer's distress of the distressful aspects of this world, Allah will rescue him from a difficulty of the difficulties of the Hereafter. Whoever alleviates [the situation of] one in dire straits who cannot repay his debt, Allah will alleviate his lot in both this world and in the Hereafter. Whoever conceals [the faults of] a Muslim, Allah will conceal [his faults] in this life and the Hereafter. Allah is helping the servant as long as the servant is helping his brother.

(Muslim, Kitab alBirr, Book 32, No.6250)

This tradition of the Prophet, (SAW), shows that Allah rewards His servants in a manner similar to the deeds that they perform. By cooperating and helping the Muslim in difficulty, Allah will surely help a person in return. This also shows what an ideal Islamic society should look like. It is a society in which its members help each other, support each other and encourage each other to do what is good.

Another relevant tradition which encourages *Takaful* is where the Prophet (SAW) is reported to have said:

عَنِ الثُّعْمَانِ بْنِ بَشِيرٍ قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ مَثَلُ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ فِي تَوَادُّهِمْ وَتَرَاحُمِهِمْ وَتَعَاطُفِهِمْ مَثَلُ الْجَسَدِ إِذَا اشْتَكَى
مِنْهُ عُضْوٌ تَدَاعَى لَهُ سَائِرُ الْجَسَدِ بِالسَّهْرِ وَالْحُمَى

صحيح البخاري كتاب الأدب باب رحمة الناس والبهائم 5665

صحيح مسلم كتاب البر والصلة والآداب باب تراحم المؤمنين وتعاطفهم وتعاضدهم 2586

Al-Nu'man ibn Bashir reported: The Messenger of Allah, (SAW), said, "The parable of the believers in their affection, mercy, and compassion for each other is that of a body. When any limb aches, the

whole body reacts with sleeplessness and fever.((Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī 6011, Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim 2586 Book 78, Hadith 42, book 73, hadith 40))

As part of the Prophet (SAW) is reported to have encourages *Takaful* through a person in difficulty where he said:

وَعَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ - رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ - قَالَ: قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ - صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ - { مَنْ نَفَسَ عَنْ مُؤْمِنٍ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ الدُّنْيَا نَفَسَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُ كُرْبَةً مِنْ كُرْبِ يَوْمِ الْقِيَامَةِ . وَمَنْ يَسِّرْ عَلَى مُعْسِرٍ ، يَسِّرَ اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ . وَمَنْ سَتَرَ مُسْلِمًا ، سَتَرَهُ اللَّهُ فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ . وَاللَّهُ فِي عَوْنِ الْعَبْدِ مَا كَانَ الْعَبْدُ فِي عَوْنِ أَخِيهِ } أَخْرَجَهُ مُسْلِمٌ .¹
¹ - صحيح. رواه مسلم (2699)، وتامامه: "ومن سلك طريقا يلتمس فيه علما، سهل الله به طريقا إلى الجنة، وما اجتمع قوم في بيت من بيوت الله، يتلون كتاب الله، ويتدارسونه بينهم، إلا نزلت عليهم السكينة، وغشيتهم الرحمة، وحفتهم الملائكة، وذكرهم الله فيمن عنده... ومن بطا به عمله، لم يسرع به نسبه."

Abu Hurairah (RAA) narrated that the Messenger of Allah (ﷺ) said: "If anyone relieves a Muslim believer from one of the hardships of this worldly life, Allah will relieve him of one of the hardships of the Day of Resurrection. If anyone makes it easy for the one who is indebted to him (while finding it difficult to repay), Allah will make it easy for him in this worldly life and in the Hereafter, and if anyone conceals the faults of a Muslim, Allah will conceal his faults in this world and in the Hereafter. Allah helps His slave as long as he helps his brother. (Muslim Book 16, Hadith 29)

It is also part of *takaful* to help the orphans and relates with them in kindness and compassion as can be seen in the following Qur'anic statement where Allah the Exalted says:

فِي الدُّنْيَا وَالْآخِرَةِ وَيَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ الْيَتَامَى قُلْ إِصْلَاحٌ لَهُمْ خَيْرٌ وَإِنْ تُخَالطُوهُمْ فَاخْوَانُكُمْ وَاللَّهُ يَعْلَمُ الْمُفْسِدَ مِنَ الْمُصْلِحِ وَلَوْ شَاءَ اللَّهُ لَأَعْنَتَكُمْ إِنَّ اللَّهَ عَزِيزٌ حَكِيمٌ (220)
...(Their bearings) on this life and the hereafter they ask you concerning orphans. Say: the best thing to do is what is for their good; if you mix their affairs with yours, they are your brethren; but Allah knows the man who means mischief from the man who means good. And if Allah had wished He could have put you into difficulties: he is indeed exalted in power, wise. (Q.2:220)
Additionally, Islam encourages the spirit of *takaful* in the form of goodness and serving ones' parents and relations:

وَاعْبُدُوا اللَّهَ وَلَا تُشْرِكُوا بِهِ شَيْئًا وَبِالْوَالِدَيْنِ إِحْسَانًا وَبِذِي الْقُرْبَى وَالْيَتَامَى وَالْمَسَاكِينِ وَالْجَارِ ذِي الْقُرْبَى وَالْجَارِ الْجُنُبِ وَالصَّاحِبِ بِالْجَنبِ وَابْنِ السَّبِيلِ وَمَا مَلَكَتْ أَيْمَانُكُمْ إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يُحِبُّ مَنْ كَانَ مُخْتَالًا فَخُورًا (36)

Serve Allah and join not any partners with him and do good to parents, kinsfolk, orphans, those in need, neighbours who are near, neighbours who are strangers, the companion by your side, the wayfarer (you meet) and what your right hands possess: for Allah loves not the arrogant, the conceited (Q.4:36)

Equally important is (Q.3:103) which encourage the spirit of co-operation among the Muslim community. Allah the exalted says:

وَاعْتَصِمُوا بِحَبْلِ اللَّهِ جَمِيعًا وَلَا تَفَرَّقُوا وَاذْكُرُوا نِعْمَتَ اللَّهِ عَلَيْكُمْ إِذْ كُنْتُمْ أَعْدَاءً فَأَلَّفَ بَيْنَ قُلُوبِكُمْ فَأَصْبَحْتُمْ بِنِعْمَتِهِ إِخْوَانًا وَكُنْتُمْ عَلَى شَفَا حُفْرَةٍ مِنَ النَّارِ فَأَنْقَذَكُمْ مِنْهَا كَذَلِكَ يُبَيِّنُ اللَّهُ لَكُمْ آيَاتِهِ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَهْتَدُونَ (103)

And hold fast, all together, by the rope which Allah (stretches out for you), and be not divided among yourselves; and remember with gratitude Allah's favour on you; for you were enemies and He joined your hearts in love, so that by His grace you became brethren; and you were on the brink of the pit of fire, and he saved you from it thus does Allah make His signs clear to you; that you may be guided. (Q.3:103)

Similarly, another tradition shows that the place of relationships and feelings of people with faith, between each other, is just like the body; when one of its parts is afflicted with pain, then the rest of the body will be affected.

عَنْ أَبِي مُوسَى عَنِ النَّبِيِّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ قَالَ إِنَّ الْمُؤْمِنِينَ لِلْمُؤْمِنِينَ كَالْبُنْيَانِ يَشُدُّ بَعْضُهُم بَعْضًا وَشَبَّكَ أَصَابِعُهُ
صحيح البخاري كتاب الصلاة أبواب استقبال القبلة باب تشبيك الأصابع في المسجد وغيره 467
صحيح مسلم كتاب البر والصلة والآداب باب تراحم المؤمنين وتعاطفهم وتعاضدهم 2585

Abu Musa reported: The Messenger of Allah (SAW), said, "Verily, the believers are like a structure, each part strengthening the other," and the Prophet clasped his fingers together.(Bukhari Book 46, Hadith 7, Vol. 3, Book 43, Hadith 626)

Additionally, it was reported that the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) participated in the *takaful* fund organized for trade journey before the epoch of Islam. The incident happened when some business men in Makkah established a kind of common fund by pooling the resources from all participating members. This form of mutual fund was used to help the victims or survivors of natural hazards during their journey flying their commercial ventures. The Prophet (SAW), also traded with the capital provided by Khadijah (ra), contributed to such fund.

Benefits of *Takaful*

Through the spirit of co-operation and joint-responsibilities among people of common interest, the act of charity and benevolence allows participants the opportunity to obtain two forms of benefits. First the monetary benefits through the *takaful* plan. Secondly the “benefits” in the spiritual sense, through the act of *Tabarru'* (donation), more importantly participants will receive Allah's grace and blessings in this life and in the Hereafter. This is mention in the following prophetic tradition. Abu Huraira reported that the Messenger of Allah, (SAW), is reported to have said:

عَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ مَا مِنْ
يَوْمٍ يُصْبِحُ الْعِبَادُ فِيهِ إِلَّا مَلَكَانِ يَنْزِلَانِ فَيَقُولُ أَحَدُهُمَا لِلَّهِمَّ أَعْطِ مُنْفِقًا خَلْفًا وَيَقُولُ الْآخَرُ لِلَّهِمَّ أَعْطِ مُمْسِكًا تَلْفًا

On the authority of Abu Hurairah (May Allah be Pleased with Him Who said), The Messenger of Allah (Peace be upon Him) said: There is not a day upon which the servant awakens but that two angels descend. One of them says: O Allah, give repayment to one who spends in charity! The other says: O Allah, give destruction to one who withholds charity! (Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī 1442, Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim 1010)

Management of *Takaful*

Five models are designed to manage *takaful*, thus:

- i) ***Takaful based on Wakalah Model***: This is a system whereby an agent is given the power to manage the *takaful* products. Based on this principle, the model describes an agency agreement between the operators, acting as the agent or “wakil” to the participant as the principal to manage the participation of the latter in a variety of *takaful* products provided by the operator.
- ii) ***Takaful based on Mudharabah model***: Basically, this system involves on profit and lost sharing between the capital provider and the manager of the capital..
- iii) ***Takaful based on Hybrid Model***: This is a mixture of *wakala* and *Mudarraba* model. Under this model, a relationship between the operator which combines the role of entrepreneur or *Mudharib* as well as the agent or *wakil* of the participant, while the latter in the capacity as both provider of capital or *sahibul-mal* and principal to the agent.
- iv) ***Takaful based on Waqf Model***: The term “*waqf*” referred for this model explains the contract of *takaful* that underlines the agreement or consent of the participants that the *takaful* contribution paid in return for participating in the *takaful* product to be credited by the operator into the *takaful* fund in accordance with the principle of *waqf* or endowment. In this case, a *waqf* account has to be established by the operator within the *takaful* fund. To this effect the operator is required to relinquish some kind of “seed” money as *waqf* to generate the said *waqf* account. This *waqf* account of the *takaful* fund will be invested similar to the three *takaful* models discussed earlier. (Saleh M. M, 2021:pp.97)
- v) ***Takaful based on Adashe Model***: The term “*adashe*” referred for this model explains the contract of *takaful* that underlines the agreement or consent of the participants that the *takaful* contribution paid on monthly bases by family members, women groups, Religious organizations, Schools Association, farmers, civil servants e.t.c. and the amount realized will be given to one or two members in the group. In this case, an *adashe* account has to be established by the group where each member will pay at the end of every month.

Nature and Characteristics of *Takaful* in Taraba State

The nature of *takaful* in Taraba is basically on *Adashe* model where family members, women groups, religious organizations, schools Associations, farmers association, civil servants etc. However, there are few *takaful* companies in Jalingo such as *Alhuda*, *Al ta awun* etc. This paper therefore focuses on the Association of Model Islamic Schools (AMIS), Taraba State chapter. The paper therefore examines the nature and benefits of *Takaful* (Islamic insurance) mutual assistance among some proprietors of AMIS.

Association of Model Islamic Schools, (AMIS)

The Association of Model Islamic Schools, (AMIS) was established by the proprietors of private Islamic schools in Nigeria, with the following desire objectives: To exchange ideas and foster mutual cooperation among private Islamic Schools in Nigeria; to engage in the formulation and implementation of policies aimed at assisting in the development and general growth of member school and to serve as training ground for member schools through seminars, workshops and conferences (AMIS Constitution ND), PP. 4-5)

Takaful among Proprietors of AMIS in Jalingo, Taraba

The specific objective of Proprietors of these schools is to compliment the effort of government in the area of education, especially at the elementary level. Part of the challenges facing the proprietor of this type of school is that of funding. Looking at the financial challenges surrounding the general administration of their Schools, AMIS Jalingo branch came up with the idea of *Takaful* among its members.

The *Adashe* model of *Takaful* was adopted, which is characterized with monthly contributions from members. The main objective of establishing this *takaful* group is to organize a system of mutual assistance among members of AMIS in Jalingo, Taraba State whereby each proprietor contributes an agreed amount from monthly earning. The idea of this mutual assistance was prompted during the covid-19 pandemic when all the schools were closed down.

This mutual assistance started in October, 2020 with five members each contributed the sum of fifty thousand Naira (N50,000.00), only. Interestingly, from July, 2021, members agreed to increase the contribution to the sum of One hundred thousand Naira (N100,000).

This shows that at the initial contribution, a benefiting member collects the sum of N250, 000, but when the contribution was increased to One hundred thousand Naira (N100, 000), a benefiting member goes home with the sum of five hundred thousand Naira N500, 000.00.

Benefit of Takaful to Proprietors of Model Islamic Schools in Jalingo

One of the most prominent features that distinguish the Muslim society from other societies is its mutual support, brotherhood and solidarity. This spirit of mutual cooperation and zeal to create wealth through lawful means is what prompted the Association of Model Islamic schools, Jalingo branch to initiate the idea of monthly contributions among its members. This mutual assistance which commenced in October, 2020 has yielded a lot of benefits to the members. The members who benefited outlined a number of projects carried out in their schools with the funds. Below is the result of the interview conducted to assess the benefits of this model of *takaful*.

Challenges of Takaful

In spite of the successes recorded and the benefits accrued through this mutual assistance among members of AMIS, there are however some challenges in its operation. From the interview conducted and the practical experience of the researcher who is a member, the following are recorded as some of the challenges facing these mutual contributions:

- i) Delay in payment of contribution by some members, which in most cases thwart the plans of a benefiting member. Due to the informal nature of this *takaful* and the fact that the contributing members sources of fund are mainly from school fees, hence delay in payment of fees will have direct effect on the contributions.
- ii) Competition in the contribution roster: Sometimes there are disagreements in the roster of benefiting member as to who will the first position.
- iii) Lack of financial discipline among members lead some members delay the payments.
- iv) Death of a member may also be challenge.

Conclusion

As a system of mutual assistance *takaful* remains a viable way for societal growth and development, since it is a system devoid of interest, a system where people cooperate in helping their brethren who are in financial difficulties and creates wealth in lawful ways. It is a common knowledge among Muslims that conventional insurance system is against the teachings of Islamic principles because of its' association with interest (*Riba*) and uncertainty(*Gharar*) Therefore *takaful* Islamic insurance and conventional insurance are diametrically opposed to each other in both substance and form because the former operates in an atmosphere devoid of interest (*Riba*), uncertainty (*Gharar*) and gambling (*Maysir*), the latter has at the very core of its embodiment, the presence of these anti-*Shari ah* features which are integral to the survival of its operations.

Consequently, given the Qur'anic injunctions to "cooperate and assist one another in goodness" and the traditions of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) regarding mutual assistance, *Takaful* may be understood as an important ingredient in the societal development and an obligation upon Muslims community to put into practice.

Islamic Mutual Financial Assistance ... (Abdullahi & Umar, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368601>

Recommendations

1. There should be effort from the AMIS members geared towards formalizing *takaful* so as to address some of the challenges arising from its' informal nature.
2. Since *takaful* practices are largely based on Islamic teachings of mutual assistance, Islamic organizations and groups like AMIS should embark on serious campaign to educate its members and general Muslims on the benefits associated with *takaful*.
3. Similarly, there should be concerted effort by Islamic scholars and *Ulama* to encourage the spirit of *takaful* among the people as the best way to resolve the economic recession among the Muslims.
4. Muslims organizations, groups and individuals should embrace this spirit of mutual assistance by pooling their resources to create wealth

References

- Abdulhamid, S., (2009), *Sahih Muslim: Condensation and Commentary*. Dar Al Arabia
- Ahmad, A. A. (2010). *Selection of Prophetic Hadiths and Muhammad Wisdoms, English Arabic, Salma A (trans)*. Dar-Al-Kotob Al-Ilmiyyah.
- Ahmad, J. A. A. (2009). *Fathul Bari* (Commentary of the authentic book of Imam Bukhari), Dar Ma'arifah, Beirut, Lebanon, Book 78, Hadith 42, vol 8, book 73, hadith 40)
- Al-Bukhari, M. I., (1981), *Sahih al-Bukhari*, Dar al- Fikr, al-Qahira.
- Al-Hashimi, M. A., Al-Khattab, N. (2007). *The Ideal Muslim society: As Define in the Qur'an and Sunnah*, International Islamic Publishing House.
- Association of Model Islamic Schools. (2010). *Constitution of Association of Model Islamic Schools*. Unpublished
- Fadli, Y., (2009), *An Overview of the Takaful Industry, An article In New Horizon Magazine*. Institute of Islamic Banking and Insurance.
- Hamidu, A. A. (2009). A Review of basic principle of Islamic finance and Interest free investment Alternative. *International Research and Advanced Studies*, 1(1), 21-30.
- Musa, A. (2014). *The Basic Principle of Takaful (Islamic Insurance)*. An Undergraduate Project, Department of Islamic studies, Taraba State University, Jalingo, Nigeria.
- Saleh M. M. (2016), *Challenges in Takaful Application Within Conventional Insurance Framework in Nigeria: The Imperative For Legislative Harmonization of Regulatory Instruments*. PhD Thesis, Faculty of Law, University Of Malaya Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.